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**Key, player, artificial intelligence and criminal liability
in European criminal law**

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Abstract: Nowadays the phenomenon of artificial intelligence is a term that was created and used initially by other sciences. The term has passed indirectly via various steps towards a legal system which is full of gaps both at national and European level. New technologies have been a topic of discussion for years not only for jurists but also for other categories of professionals. Unfortunately, the European reality that interests us in this paper has shown that the time has now come to try to regulate what is called artificial intelligence as well as the role it plays in our society. Our paper focuses on the criminal liability of the person who deals with an algorithmic machine. However, is it a criminal liability that falls only on the person or does it also involve the machine? The questions are many, and the European path in this sector is still obscure and on primitive steps. Surely in the near future we would talk more precisely about the criminal liability that covers this sector.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; criminal liability; European Union criminal law; good; AI society; accountability; liability; human oversight; human-in-the loop.

Introduction

Since evidence collected in a technological and digital way in international and national criminal trials, we have started talking about artificial intelligence (AI) (Freitas et al., 2014; Hallevy, 2015; Gless, Silverman, Weigend, 2016; Müller, Bostrom, 2016; Seher, 2016; Kowert, 2017; Simmler, Markwalder, 2017; Pagallo, Quattrocchio, 2018; Abbott, Sarch, 2019; Burchard, 2019; Palace, 2019; Hu, 2019; Lagioia, Sartor, 2020; Nersessian, Mancha, 2021; Kovac, 2022; Günsberg, 2022)¹. The diffusion of this system of new technologies as well as of the AI that function in our daily life in an autonomous and unexpected way remains questionable both because the veracity of these evidences are difficult to demonstrate but also because we do not know if it exists and if yes what is the relative responsibility that machines have. In other words, these are doubts that enter the national, European, international criminal sphere and seek an answer (Pagallo, 2018).

¹European Commission, High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, A definition of AI: Main capabilities and scientific disciplines, 2018: https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/system/files/ged/ai_hleg_definition_of_ai_18_december_1.pdf.

With the expression artificial intelligence we speak:

“(...) of machines equipped with a very significant calculation capacity. Artificial intelligence systems are, in fact, computers (and computer programs) that combine large amounts of data (so-called Big Data), with the aim of learning how to manage future decision-making processes (...). These are not machines capable of making real decisions, but more simply of drawing certain conclusions from the data that can be deduced from previous experiences (...)”(Gillespie, 2014).

Already at the European level we have the European Parliament which, through the Resolution of October 2021 “Artificial intelligence in criminal law” put the first ideas on the subject by stating:

“(...) a clear and fair regime for attributing legal responsibility and imputability of the potential negative consequences produced by these advanced digital technologies (...)”².

No attention was paid to the related criminal liability as the Resolution did not provide instructions but concentrated generally on the European dimension. The various questions due to the continuous technological progress and the relationship with the criminal law have started to play an important role since we have been told about a shock of modernity (Wells, 2011). In our opinion we can speak of a particular type of liability for damage caused by a product that was defective in the area of environmental crimes. It is a not very developed area but criminal law was always a tool to punish, to compensate and the difference in national or European criminal law always

²European Parliament resolution of 2021 on artificial intelligence in criminal law and its use by police and judicial authorities in criminal matters (2020/2016(INI)), 13: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2021-0405_EN.html

remains a topic under discussion and also difficult to arrive at concrete conclusive results (Abbott, Sarch, 2019).

According to Abbott and Sarch,

“AI systems raise an irreducibility problem for criminal law (the so-called “irreducibility challenge”) as it could be extremely difficult, if not impossible, to reduce a crime committed by an AI system to the action of an individual human being (Santoni De Sio, Mecacci, 2021). Four characteristics are possessed by AI systems: autonomy, i.e. the ability to cause a harmful event without the system being directed to do so by a human agent; opacity, i.e. the impossibility-especially when dealing with more advanced systems such as those based on deep learning (Hao, 2018) - of being able to obtain an explanation on how the system, starting from the input (A), obtained the harmful output (B); complexity, i.e. the fact that the creation of an AI system is often the result of the contribution of many individuals, developed over a long period of time, as well as the fact that the system may have been trained on databases heterogeneous and open source; and finally unpredictability, i.e. the ability for the system to undertake activities not foreseen by its original programming (...)” (Abbott, Sarch, 2019).

After these first statements it is noted that the criminal attribution of responsibility towards man/men is open to an intelligent system. Among the first questions is the omissive conduct that has to do with a juridical duty and a fact that presents itself as an impediment to an event.

On the other hand, human responsibility needs a position of guarantee, as well as the existence of a precautionary rule as a consequence of a positive attitude or one based on the experience and configurability of a model agent. Furthermore, does the knowability of a rule also mean the predictability of a criminal event or not? We need the enforceability of a behavior that conforms to the human being. This contribution has peculiar

characteristics that interacts with the AI both on the subject of responsibility and also on the title of guilt.

Involvement with an AI system as we understand it is very complex due to the paucity of scientific knowledge of this type of technology as well as the lack of a foundation of conventions on the subject. There are no ad hoc rules that can be known by the human agent, just as the machine must exercise the relative control since it is built, organized to prevail. The harmful event should be prevented and is unpredictable.

First of all, an analysis of the accountability is needed (Novelli, Taddeo, Floridi, 2023) which approaches the theme of the AI-regulation after the notion of the impact area of the AI and its relationship with criminal matters. Of course, this does not outline the line of an area-operation circle that is carried out in assessments on the extent of the impact of the AI in a specific sector of criminal law. For once again the European Parliament of October 2021 entitled: “Artificial intelligence in criminal law” and the related proposal for a European regulation known as the AI Act³ are steps forward on the notion of human surveillance (“human oversight”)⁴ which opens the debate of the identification of the relationship between this notion and

³European Commission, Proposal for a regulation of the European parliament and of the council establishing harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (law on artificial intelligence) and amending certain legislative acts of the union, COM/2021/206, 21 April 2021: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021PC0206>

⁴<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-11124-2022-INIT/en/pdf>

criminal guilt.

It is obvious that more from national criminal law we focus on European law. Over time, a new discussion impact is quickly acquired in the European context that approaches towards the regulation of artificial intelligence and the creation of the “good AI society” (Floridi and others, 2018; Roberts, 2021), including also such sector in the work of the European institutions, given that the continuous evolution of AI systems (Ravidran, 2020) are the basis for the objectives of the European criminal policy.

Within this context, the Europol Innovation Lab has published a report on crimes committed using deepfake technologies (Thi Nguyen, T. et al., 2019) proposing:

“(...) the emergence of new forms of crime for the next decade, which will bring with them many difficulties from the point of view of the attribution of criminal responsibility (...)”⁵.

Continuing with the project “Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence” (AP4AI)⁶, which brings together Eurojust, Europol, CEPOL as well as the research centre: Center of Excellence in Terrorism, Resilience, Intelligence and Organized Crime Research (CENTRIC)⁷ as a development basis of a chain of creation of principles that guarantee the ethical, transparent and responsible utility of AI systems especially in

⁵Europol (2022), Facing reality? Law enforcement and the challenge of deepfakes, an observatory report from the Europol Innovation Lab, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 16.

⁶<https://www.ap4ai.eu/>

⁷<https://www.netlaw.bg/en/a/centric-centre-of-excellence-in-terrorism-resilience-intelligence-and-organised-crime-research-sheffield-hallam-university-united-kingdom#>

law enforcement agencies.

Accountability, responsibility and liability, Are they new penal concepts?

When we talk about accountability in the AI sector we mean its regulation and development in an ethical way through the use of soft law principles rather than its elaboration by relative hard law tools⁸.

The notion of accountability has been referred to in the Artificial Intelligence High-Level Expert Group (AI HLEG) which was established by the European Commission in the document entitled: “Ethical Guidelines” which:

“(...) represents a recurring element in initiatives of European regulation (Barrio Andrés, 2021; Kerrigan, 2022)⁹, as well as in the broader global panorama of the so-called AI ethics (...)” (Jobim and others, 2019; Thi Nguyen, 2019; Fjeld, 2020)¹⁰.

The doctrine in this regard characterizes accountability as a sufficient ethical tool to regulate the AI. Its is represented by the example of an ethics that includes a “juridical conception” (Anscombe, 1968), such as:

⁸President of the Republic of 14 April 2021 (Ordonnance n° 2021-443 du 14 avril 2021 relative au régime de responsabilité pénale applicable en cas de circulation d'un véhicule à délégation de conduite et à ses conditions d'utilisation, TRAT2034523R).

⁹Resolution of the European Parliament, Framework on the ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies, 2020/2012(INL), 20 October 2020, artt. 9, 22, 23, 72, 96, 102: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2020-0275_EN.html

¹⁰See for example: OCSE, Recommendation of the Council on Artificial Intelligence, OECD/LEGAL/0449, 2019). UNESCO, Recommendation on the ethics of artificial intelligence, SHS/BIO/REC-AIETHICS/2021, 2021).

“(…) a sort of draft of the law (…) where ethics is not “toothless” at all but is simply used in the wrong way (…)” (Rességuier, Rodrigues, 2020; Munn, 2022).

If so, what would be the meaning of the word accountability and what kind of relationship or link does it have with criminal liability?

Accountability does not mean responsibility of liability despite the fact that it is a notion that is connected with many notions of responsibility. Liability includes the willful or unintentional actions either of a person or of others. As far as the actions of others are concerned, the legal situation results in the violation of an obligation and at the same time also in an unlawful act, i.e. an obligation, the ability to report. Thus accountability does not include responsibility but has the duty to suffer the relative consequences, i.e. it is an attitude that uses the capacity of an obligation that takes into consideration a social system. The boundaries between accountability, responsibility and liability¹¹ are difficult to be distinguished. Liability has to do with qualified conduct, accountability and responsibility have a broader notion that also contains rules of a moral and social nature as well as standards of courtesy.

Accountability is defined as a notion of a procedural nature that symbolizes the accused or who being placed in the dock typical elements of European criminal trials and also of the common

¹¹https://commission.europa.eu/business-economy-euro/doing-business-eu/contract-rules/digital-contracts/liability-rules-artificial-intelligence_en

law given that they appear before a universal community (Kool, 2014; Ausserladscheider Jonas, 2021):

“(...) l’accountability is the process aimed at a subsequent public assessment of a person’s conduct in a given case in order to evaluate whether this conduct was required and/or justified by this person’s responsibility and, once this evaluation is executed, to establish who can be held liable for all consequences of the conduct (...)” (Giesen, Kristen, 2014).

According to Duff:

“(...) responsibility is a “relational” concept, since it concerns the relationship that is established between a responsible person (A), an object (X) for which this person is responsible, and a third party (B). This is called “answerability””(Duff, 2005; Duff, 2009; Duff, 2019).

As far as liability is concerned, we are referring exclusively to the situation of a person who performs a certain action in stipulating a specific contract, i.e. a legal obligation and its related legal consequences arising from it. Also in this problematic Duff stated ex novo that:

“(...) we can have (criminal) responsibility without necessarily having (criminal) liability. Consider, for example, the case of a crime committed in the absence of illegality (...)” (Duff, 2005).

In the European context, to avoid technical confusion, especially for jurists, the word responsibility was preferred in a unique way¹².

Accountability comes in various dimensional forms since criminal liability is one of them (Heyns, 2016). Accountability is thus founded in the traditional way on a notion that includes the relative control. Control that has to do with constituent

¹²European Parliament, Resolution on artificial intelligence: questions relating to the interpretation and application of international law as far as the EU is concerned in relation to civilian and military uses and state authority outside the area of criminal justice, (2020/2013(INI)), recital I, artt. 14, 24, 25, 49, 52, 70, 72: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2021-0009_EN.html

elements of the crime such as a dominable conduct of the perpetrator (Keiler, 2013) and in a causal link with criminal liability (Ashworth, 2009; Blomsma, 2012; Keiler, 2013; Keiler, Roef, 2019). Criminal liability is imposed on those who are aware of their actions as well as the implications of their actions or inactions in such a way as to be able to affirm that they have chosen a certain behavior (Ashworth, 2009). And how do all these first affirmations of responsibility enter, work and bring consequences to an algorithmic action?

Finally, trying to analyze the relationship of responsibility and the linguistic nuances it uses, it is understood that the relationship between AI and criminal law is based on a relationship between conflict and collaboration (Vuletić, Petrašević, 2020). The conflict zone leads back to the substantive criminal law which directs a human subject as responsible.

The Resolution of the European Parliament “Artificial intelligence in criminal law” and the Artificial Intelligence Act

On 6 October 2021, The European Parliament approved a Resolution entitled: “Artificial intelligence in criminal law and its use by police and judicial authorities in the criminal field”¹³.

¹³European Parliament resolution of 2021 on artificial intelligence in criminal law and its use by police and judicial authorities in criminal matters

This is not a resolution of a binding nature but a starting point which develops the related considerations that guide the EU to the related profiles of criminal liability that are connected with the AI. In European criminal law also there is not yet a general part where we can include the related systems of the AI. This gap, as we can see later, generates transversal and dogmatic problems (Klip, 2021).

However, in art. 13 the Resolution just mentioned included the notion of legal responsibility and liability as a potential prejudicial effect of the AI systems that are used in the context of criminal justice. According to art. 13. the European Parliament also extends this resolution to other areas:

“(...) where the use of AI is growing, and connected to the complexity of the development and functioning of these technologies (...). The creation of an AI system requires the contribution of multiple people, organizations, mechanical components, algorithms, software and human users in often complex and problematic environments (...)”¹⁴.

Thus, it is important to establish a mechanism of an attributive nature as referred to in art. 13. The recital J also states that:

“(...) a clear model is needed for attributing responsibility for the potential harmful effects of AI systems in the field of criminal law (...)”¹⁵.

(2020/2016(INI)).

¹⁴European Parliament resolution of 2021 on artificial intelligence in criminal law and its use by police and judicial authorities in criminal matters (2020/2016(INI)), recital I.

¹⁵European Parliament resolution of 2021 on artificial intelligence in criminal law and its use by police and judicial authorities in criminal matters (2020/2016(INI)): “J. whereas a clear model for assigning legal responsibility for the potential harmful effects of AI systems in the field of criminal law is imperative; whereas regulatory provisions in this field should always maintain human accountability and must aim, first and foremost, to avoid causing any harmful effects to begin (...)”.

Regulatory rules in this area should always uphold human responsibility and their first and foremost aim must above all be the prevention of any adverse effects¹⁶.

Regulatory provisions always guarantee “human accountability” and so the word responsibility or liability is not used in them, given that they have a different basis that intersects with an offense which does not necessarily include a legal liability. The recital J we can say that it is in contrast with art. 13 that:

“(...) takes note of the challenges relating to the correct identification of legal responsibility and liability for potential damages, given the complexity of the development and functioning of AI systems; considers it necessary to set up a clear and fair regime for attributing legal responsibility and accountability for the potential negative consequences produced by such advanced digital technologies; stresses, however, that the first and foremost aim must above all be the prevention of such consequences (...)”¹⁷.

Here we see that the notions of legal responsibility and liability are used in the words of legal responsibility and imputability.

The use of these words shows the effort of the European

¹⁶European Parliament resolution of 2021 on artificial intelligence in criminal law and its use by police and judicial authorities in criminal matters (2020/2016(INI)), recital J.

¹⁷European Parliament resolution of 2021 on artificial intelligence in criminal law and its use by police and judicial authorities in criminal matters (2020/2016(INI)), art. 13: “Recognises the challenges to the correct location of legal responsibility and liability for potential harm, given the complexity of development and operation of AI systems; considers it necessary to create a clear and fair regime for assigning legal responsibility and liability for the potential adverse consequences produced by these advanced digital technologies; underlines, however, that the aim must, first and foremost, be to prevent any such consequences materialising to begin with; calls, therefore, for the application of the precautionary principle in all applications of AI in the context of law enforcement; underlines that legal responsibility and liability must always rest with a natural or legal person, who must always be identified for decisions taken with the support of AI; emphasises, therefore, the need to ensure the transparency of the corporate structures that produce and manage AI systems (...)”.

Parliament to put more precisely the type of responsibility that the legal consequences derive from. Thus the liability as well as the legal responsibility carry legal responsibilities as we read in the recital J and the term liability means, in our opinion, imputability which in criminal law represents a different meaning from that of liability.

In the recital J the guarantee of a form of human accountability, *rectius* responsibility is discussed. Instead art. 13 establishes the relative obligation for both a natural and legal person to be legally responsible and liable for the relative decisions that are taken with the support of a system of the AI. It is a matter of an obligatory figure of the accountable human or of a “legally responsible and liable human” who bring into play the accountability guaranteed with non-criminal instruments, of auditing procedures which always guarantee an identified criminal subject who is responsible in force of the position of guarantee where one's subjectibility to the type of crime is provided for in the individual legal systems, and with the relative difficulties that apply and that derive from the same recitals that we analyze.

The European Parliament Resolution through art. 13 seeks to consistently apply the precautionary principle for all related applications of the AI that enter into law enforcement, as it underlines the legal responsibility and imputability that falls on

natural or legal persons who identify the decisions taken with the support of the AI, thus emphasizing the security and transparency of the companies that produce and manage AI systems¹⁸. Thus the first and main objective of a prevention with negative effects that is inspired by the precautionary principle is framed. The invocation of this principle immediately makes us think of the criminal law of the risk that is proposed by the European regulation presented by the European Commission itself during April of 2021 entitled as: “AI Act”¹⁹.

The AI Act is based on a risk-based approach. The regulation establishes a few different levels of risk which are concentrated on the used positions of: unacceptable, high risk, low or minimal risk. Each level of risk also corresponds to the obligations and requirements of the high-risk system, arriving at what interests us, namely human oversight. Human intervention provides for the measure to prevent, i.e. govern a risk that occurs with detrimental effects that are caused by an AI system. The human supervisor will be one of the responsible subjects where this risk materializes and is in default of his/her surveillance obligations, i.e. of the relative subjects who are “legally responsible and

¹⁸European Parliament resolution of 2021 on artificial intelligence in criminal law and its use by police and judicial authorities in criminal matters (2020/2016(INI)), art. 13.

¹⁹European Commission, Proposal for a regulation of the European parliament and of the council establishing harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (law on artificial intelligence) and amending certain legislative acts of the union, 2021/0106(COD), 21 April 2021.

liable as per the aforementioned article 13”.

The AI Act through the recital 48 seeks to affirm the related human surveillance measures that are adequate to guarantee that the system:

“(...) responds to the human operator, and that the natural persons who have been entrusted with human surveillance have the skills, training and authority necessary to carry out this role (...)”²⁰.

Continuing with article 14 of the AI Act which states:

“(...) to prevent or minimize the risks to health, safety or fundamental rights which may arise when a high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose or under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse (...)”²¹.

Paragraph 4 includes:

“(...) a detailed list of the actions that should be implemented by those entrusted with human surveillance. These include, for example, the functioning of the high-risk AI system or its interruption by means of a “stop” button or similar procedure (Art. 14, c. 4, lett. e) (...)”.

Despite all this European effort we do not yet have a binding force in our hands which represents an evolutionary clue not so much in European criminal law as in the creation of a regulatory framework which starts from the basis of carrying out the related reflections which take shape as challenges for the evolution of the EU law and above all the recognition of individual conduct of human oversight²² and the attribution of

²⁰European Commission, Proposal for a regulation of the European parliament and of the council establishing harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (law on artificial intelligence) and amending certain legislative acts of the union, op. cit.

²¹European Commission, Proposal for a regulation of the European parliament and of the council establishing harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (law on artificial intelligence) and amending certain legislative acts of the union, op. cit., art. 14, lett. c).

²²<https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation/guidelines/1.html>

responsibility for fault.

Human oversight and/or human-in-the loop

Autonomous work in the AI systems results in the malfunctioning of the mechanisms for attributing criminal responsibility. The AI Act offered a first solution on it as it was based on the notion of human surveillance using the so-called human-in-the loop term (HITL) (Enarsson, Enqvist, Naartijärvi, 2022)²³. It is a realization of the AI systems where the output model is developed with the interaction of a human agent who plays the role of the teacher in the training phase of the system thus providing feedback to the machine which obtains the result (Wu, 2021).

For some, the connection of the human being in the loop of AI:

“(...) could seem prima facie a reassuring solution, based on a circular logic that is distracted by the intrinsically harmful uses of automated systems. Policymakers are turning to humans to mitigate the risks posed by AI systems based on the assumption that humans are actually able to oversee their decision-making processes (...) the concept of human oversight seems to be used as a sort of miraculous ointment, to remedy the potential risks posed by algorithmic action. The real risk, however, is that of making the man who supervises a scapegoat, in clear contrast with the general principles of our criminal law, in particular with the refusal of strict liability (...)” (Green, Kaka, 2021).

Of course there are many questions. Already in the field of AI human oversight and accountability continue to proceed closely.

²³European Commission, Proposal for a regulation of the European parliament and of the council establishing harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (law on artificial intelligence) and amending certain legislative acts of the union, op. cit., art. 14.

The concepts of supervision do not allow us to immediately arrive at human oversight or criminal liability. Why? Why does human surveillance work as a position holder which is secured by a human or a machine? And on the other hand, the European discipline on human oversight is still in an embryonic stage and the precautionary rules of conduct have not yet been established.

Conflicts and warranty positions

As can be understood, it is obvious that a position of guarantee is needed for the person who controls the AI system. This control includes protection and also the distinction between non-compliance with a guarantee obligation and non-compliance with a duty of care. We can identify the potential warranty position and the semi-autonomous driving that a driver carries out inside a vehicle. This is not a simple vehicle like a car but a much more complicated machine that activates the driving system of an intervention in the driver who takes control of the car (Banks, 2014)²⁴.

The vehicle inspector does not mean that has the full responsibility in the event of the omission of a harmful event. In our case, the inspector who puts the vehicle into circulation has the risk of the *demande de reprise*²⁵. The transfer of control of

²⁴According to Banks: “(...) hands and feet free but not “mind free” driving (...)”.

²⁵See: Ordonnance n° 2021-443 du 14 avril 2021 relative au régime de responsabilité pénale applicable en cas de circulation d'un véhicule à délégation de

the activity of a risky nature that performs to the vehicle results in the liability of a driver who steers poorly and bears the associated risks. The problem and the question is the reference to the case of an omissive liability where the liability has to do with a culpable permissive conduct when the control activity can fall within the scope of application of the ordinary rules that have to do with the circulation. The problem is legality since European sources and internal legislation do not expressly provide for anything and given the interpretative possibility of AI systems within the application sphere of the related legal guarantee obligations that are already existing based on the related technologies and the effort towards this direction which may be suitable for identifying the guarantor who is invested the obligation and holder of an effective power of impediment according to the founding principles of criminal law. The conception, production, marketing and use of the systems of the AI in the course of this process, i.e. many hands problems, lead to the relative responsibility. An all-encompassing position entails the identified obligation of the human overseer that foresees any damage that is caused by an AI system that is contrary to the principle of taxability.

And in the case of omissive liability, the subjective element meets with the problems that the AI systems have raised with

conduite et à ses conditions d'utilisation:

<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000043370894/2023-03-03>

the ascertainment of the causal link and the profile of the impossibility of preventing the event. The explanation linked to the possibility for humans to dominate a certain event and the AI system simply leads to a set of inputs and outputs that is not only difficult to explain but also to answer. Which inputs lead to the related outputs? What is human behavior and its consequences of a harmful nature that increases in tempis? The action of AI systems collides with the simultaneous presence of both human and not alternative causal factors (Hildebrandt, 2014; Santoni De Sio, Mecacci, 2021)²⁶.

Conflicts and the subjective element of crime

Speaking of the conception of the AI system as a culprit we must take into consideration that:

“(...) the possibility of identifying a real culpability-and not a simulacrum of the same-in the hands of an AI system raises (...) not few difficulties, logical and ontological (...)”.

Some scientists who deal with robotics (Pagallo, 2018) speak of liberation or rather of the words of the Chopra and White

²⁶According to Santoni de Sio and Mecacci: “(...) a vehicle may be operated by a driver D1, with the assistance of the automated driving system AS, produced by the car manufacturer X, powered with digital systems developed by the company Y, possibly including some form of machine learning developed by the company Z, and enriched by data coming from different sources, including the driving experience of drivers D2, D3 (...) Dn; vehicles in this system are in principle subject to a standardisation process done by the agency S, the traffic is regulated by the governmental agency G, drivers are trained and licensed by the agency L etc. Second, some specific features of present-day learning AI systems may make this interaction particularly unpredictable-typically when the vehicles’ performance is potentially redesigned by the second on the basis of new data acquisition and processing-and opaque, if the reasoning scheme underlying systems’ actions is not easily accessible to their controllers, regulators, or even their designers (...)”.

(Chopra, White, 2011):

“(...) robots will be capable of sensitivity to the command of the criminal law and will therefore be reproachable by punishment (...). We cannot speak of robotic guilt, because AI systems lack self-awareness (that is, they are not aware of being conscious), free will and moral autonomy (...)”.

A second path is found and related to human responsibility involving the human behind the machine. Why are we interested in this trend? Because it has to do with the negligent charge, as an area of permitted risk that makes us feel the health and transport sector in national criminal law. Linking to the system of the AI we must also have the relative technical-scientific knowledge for the application of the rules of conduct that persist in a specific way to the new cases that these systems cause and develop again from time to time. The invocation of the precautionary principle by the European authorities is adequate and in a general way this principle serves the choices of legislative policy rather than those of penalisation. Thus we get to exceed the thresholds of requests that have to do with the adoption of new rules of a precautionary nature thanks to progress in scientific laws that enter into the reconstruction and explanation of AI systems that are more complex. Creating a programming fault drops responsibility for damages that are committed by the creator's own creature. Who is to blame at this point? How can we talk about precautionary rules and the related conduct of the implementation of an AI system? And is the conduct of the human being? And who is the human agent

who bears the responsibility?

Our attention falls on the potential controller who autonomously or semi-autonomously uses an AI-based system. Let's talk about automation complacency (Giannini, Kwik, 2023) which is connected with plane crashes and the phenomenon of task automation which leads the human supervisor to trust that the machine that takes care of it effectively is the consequence to stop continuing attention (Wiener, 1981; Parasuraman & Manzey, 2010; Smiley, 2022). And in a second way where the automation bias (Završnik, 2020), obvious the tendency of the human being who brings excessive trust in the relative recommendations that are the products of a computer system as an amplified phenomenon that the AI reduce the attentions of the human agent struggling with the machine as they also decrease the threshold of the enforceability of a diligent conduct on the part of the same.

We can think that the supervisor is the one who examines the sources and notes how attention is given to the roles covered in the development chain of an AI system. On the other hand, the reference to the figure of the programmer becomes an epicenter of criminal liability. The AI team includes the various figures including the data analyst and the data scientists who deal with the interpretation of data in a pertinent and exhaustive way. Data and machine learning engineers build a machine learning fabric

and its programmers turn the model into code. The roles are cumulative with that of the user where the subject who operates the system of the AI corresponds, is equivalent to the type of responsible model agent.

Of course there is also the issue of criminal liability which is connected with the errors and inadequacy of the training data of the AI system. Machine learning based systems are so fast and hungry for new processing data. The more foods you pass, the more tagged and accurate the data is for your prediction. The aim of course is the classification and provision of possible types of classifications of data such as databases that are riddled with errors (Kang and others, 2022). Systems of the AI are databases that are flawed and are used for critical environments where wrong generalization is fatal. We recall the Uber case (Wakabayashi, 2018), as an accident that was caused by a problem:

“(...) of inability of the vehicle software to identify the presence of a pedestrian crossing on the road without using the pedestrian crossing (...)”²⁷. What if the algorithm was trained on the bad data after downloading bad or distorted data? In this case who is responsible? Data collection and generation, labeling and evaluation of one's own qualities are essential to avoid those

²⁷“The system never classified her as a pedestrian-or correctly predicted her path-because she was crossing N. Mill Avenue at a location without a crosswalk, and the system design did not include consideration for jaywalking pedestrians”. National Transportation Safety Board, Collision Between Vehicle Controlled by Developmental Automated Driving System and Pedestrian, Tempe, Arizona, March 18, 2018, Highway Accident Report NTSB/HAR-19/03, 16.

who make mistakes, as well as the verification of harmful events. On the other hand, perhaps they have not sufficiently gained the relative popularity that has to do with the analysis of a criminal nature at national and European level. Within that context we think of the “Data Centric AI”²⁸ (DCAI) movement, which focuses on the engineering of machine learning and the related modeling of the data that underlies and uses it for model training and evaluation.

The error of the supervisor and the damage caused by an AI system lead back to a malfunction that raises problems for the system, i.e. not only liability for damage from a defective product but also an error committed which, during the training of the algorithm, may be in same line as a mistake having to do with assembling a car. However in short we can say that the system of the AI as a result of the cooperation of a still very complex model.

Concluding remarks

Talking about criminal liability in the AI system is not a new and even exhaustive topic. From time to time and also in films they speak of evil robots where human responsibility has to do with the control of machines that are going crazy and act in a crazy and uncontrollable way (Floridi, 2016; Ellul, 2022)²⁹. Of

²⁸<https://datacentricai.org>

²⁹Think instead of the false Maria in Metropolis (1927); Hal 9000 in 2001: A

course, as we have seen in the European sector, the purpose is the regulation of the illicit conduct of the AI (Lehman-Wilzing, 1981; Chesterman, 2021). The reflections are many and not exhausted. The profiles of criminal liability remain the same, i.e. causal link, willful misconduct, fault. The key for the player in this sector is the global examination of a complex problem which is limited to the analysis of the so-called conflict zones where the possible connection profiles have to do with the concept of human oversight and the criminal liability of guilt. The diagnosis of responsibility remains ambiguous and until now European criminal law has not helped to clarify it by providing for example elements of monitoring and evaluation that help the national legislator to better identify the responsible person and to protect and evolve the technology for human use.

Space Odyssey (1968)(...); C3PO in Star Wars (1977); Rachael in Blade Runner (1982); Data in Star Trek: The Next Generation (1987); Agent Smith in The Matrix (1999) or the disembodied Samantha in Her (2013).

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